

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Cobalt(II) Complexes with 2-Pyrazolin-5-One Derivatives

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Twenty-six cobalt(II) complexes have been synthesised having the composition $(CoL_2)X_2$, where $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- and $L=4,4'$ -arylidene-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-one). All these complexes have a tetrahedral configuration as inferred from analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infra-red and electronic spectral studies. These 26 complexes have been screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. All these complexes are found to be active against these two pathogens. Some of the complexes are compared well with standard fungicides like O-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 60% WP.

5-PYRAZOLONE and its derivatives have been reported to possess strong antibacterial, antihistaminic and antifungal¹ activities. Although a lot of work have been done in this field by different group of workers²⁻⁴, no systematic approach has yet been made to study the fungicidal activity of those substituted pyrazolones complexed with common divalent transitional metal ions. Therefore, we thought it worthwhile to study the complexation behaviour of pyrazolones with cobalt(II) ion and also to find out the antifungal activity of these compounds upon incorporation to metal ion sphere.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. 2-Pyrazolin-5-one derivatives have been synthesised following the method reported earlier⁵.

Synthesis of complexes :

An ethanolic solution of pyrazolone derivatives were reacted separately with cobaltous salt solution in ethanol in stoichiometric ratio and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs over a water bath. On keeping overnight, crystalline compounds separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The metal contents were estimated by edta titration and nitrogen by the standard micro analytical method. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the complexes using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on the solids by the Gouy method using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant. IR spectra were recorded in KBr in the 200-4000 cm^{-1} range using Beckman IR-12 Spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilger-Watt UVISPECK Spectrophotometer with a M/100 chloroform solution of the complexes.

The relevant analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir spectral and fungitoxicity data are enlisted in Table 1. The fungicidal data of the free ligands are bracketed in the table.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type $(CoL_2) X_2$, where $L=4,4'$ -arylidene-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-one), $X=Cl^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- . The complexes have high melting points and are either blue or gray in colour. Acetone solution of the complexes have ΔM values more than 150 mhos cm^2 indicating 1:2 electrolytic nature of the complexes. The complexes have magnetic moments characteristic of a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

Pyrazolone derivatives behave as bidentate ligands involving two carbonyl oxygen atoms as the possible bonding sites. The appearance of a strong band in the free pyrazolone derivatives around 1745 cm^{-1} (where $L=4, 4'$ -arylidene-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-one) and around 1620 cm^{-1} (where $L=4, 4'$ -methylene-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-one), is attributed to the carbonyl stretch. The lowering of carbonyl stretch by about 10-15 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicates that the co-ordination of the pyrazolone derivatives to cobalt is through the carbonyl oxygens. However, conclusive evidence regarding the bonding of oxygen atoms have been provided by the occurrence of $\nu(Co-O)$ around 440 cm^{-1} in the complexes⁶.

In the electronic spectra of complexes in chloroform solution, two absorption bands are noticed ~ 16.0 (1450) and 8.0 (200) k.k. region attributable to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) transition⁷ respectively. The other transition is not observed probably because of its very weak intensity due to orbital selection rule. The high value of the ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transition and magnetic moment values support a tetrahedral configuration of the complexes.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	Compounds	% Co Found (Reqd)	% N Found (Reqd)	Δm mhos cm ²	μ eff. B. M.	$\frac{\nu(\text{C=O})}{\nu(\text{Co-O})}$	% Inh. at 1000 ppm con p. ory/H. ory.
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	5.58 (5.87)	10.99 (11.17)	220	4.40	1730 (440)	100 (84)/78 (70)
2.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(o)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	5.14 (5.39)	12.65 (12.82)	230	4.42	1730 (440)	100 (30)/85 (31)
3.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	5.17 (5.39)	12.63 (12.82)	215	4.50	1735 (450)	100 (86)/72 (48)
4.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(p)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	5.26 (5.39)	12.57 (12.82)	198	4.40	1732 (440)	100 (65)/69 (68)
5.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ N ₄ CH ₂ O ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	5.38 (5.54)	10.28 (10.54)	212	4.40	1730 (440)	78 (75)/60 (50)
6.	C ₆ H ₅	H	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	6.71 (6.93)	12.97 (13.17)	225	4.40	1610 (445)	100 (70)/85 (37)
7.	H	C ₆ H ₅	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	8.23 (8.43)	15.83 (16.04)	218	4.60	1735 (450)	93 (70)/76 (58)
8.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(o)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	7.26 (7.47)	17.60 (17.76)	195	4.38	1730 (450)	90 (39)/64 (37)
9.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	7.21 (7.47)	17.52 (17.76)	178	4.50	1730 (440)	88 (75)/70 (40)
10.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(p)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	7.28 (7.47)	17.43 (17.76)	227	4.40	1735 (435)	92 (60)/75 (75)
11.	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	7.62 (7.77)	14.53 (14.77)	235	4.40	1735 (430)	90 (58)/62 (34)
12.	H	H	(CoL ₂) Cl ₂	10.59 (10.78)	20.28 (20.51)	205	4.60	1605 (440)	92 (39)/75 (32)
13.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	5.26 (5.40)	10.08 (10.26)	230	4.50	1730 (440)	84 (84)/70 (70)
14.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	4.77 (4.98)	11.65 (11.85)	215	4.40	1735 (430)	89 (86)/65 (48)
15.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	4.92 (5.11)	9.61 (9.73)	218	4.40	1730 (445)	89 (75)/70 (50)
16.	C ₆ H ₅	H	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	6.05 (6.27)	11.80 (11.93)	205	4.50	1610 (430)	96 (70)/64 (37)
17.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(o)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	6.58 (6.71)	15.83 (15.96)	198	4.60	1738 (440)	96 (39)/88 (75)
18.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	6.61 (6.71)	15.81 (15.96)	213	4.40	1730 (440)	64 (40)/96 (60)
19.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(p)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	6.54 (6.71)	15.79 (15.96)	223	4.40	1730 (435)	70 (75)/96 (58)
20.	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O ^(m)	(CoL ₂) Br ₂	6.78 (6.95)	13.05 (13.22)	198	4.50	1730 (450)	70 (34)/85 (70)
21.	H	C ₆ H ₅	(CoL ₂) (NO ₂) ₂	7.69 (7.84)	18.47 (18.64)	225	4.50	1735 (450)	70 (58)/88 (39)
22.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(o)	(CoL ₂) (NO ₂) ₂	6.83 (7.00)	19.83 (19.97)	220	4.40	1735 (440)	73 (37)/100 (75)
23.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(m)	(CoL ₂) (NO ₂) ₂	6.87 (7.00)	19.81 (19.97)	235	4.60	1730 (440)	65 (40)/100 (60)
24.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ ^(p)	(CoL ₂) (NO ₂) ₂	6.90 (7.00)	19.75 (19.97)	228	4.40	1730 (440)	80 (75)/88 (58)
25.	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O ^(m)	(CoL ₂) (NO ₂) ₂	7.05 (7.26)	17.08 (17.26)	195	4.40	1730 (440)	80 (34)/100 (39)
26.	H	H	(CoL) (NO ₂) ₂	9.65 (9.83)	23.10 (23.37)	220	4.50	1610 (445)	80 (32)

The ligands and the 26 complexes prepared during the present investigation were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* by the standard method⁹ using spore germination tests at various concentrations. All the complexes showed encouraging fungicidal activity against these two pathogens.

Out of the twelve complexes of the type $(CoL_2) Cl_2$, the complexes (Sl. No. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6) showed 100% germination inhibition and complexes (Sl. No. 7, 8, 10, 11 and 12) showed above 90% germination inhibition at 1000 ppm concentration of the pathogen *P. oryzae*. The complexes (Sl. No. 2 and 6) showed 85% spore germination inhibition at 1000 ppm concentration of the pathogen *H. oryzae*.

In case of the complexes of the type $(CoL_2) Br_2$, the complexes (Sl. No. 16, 17, 19 and 20) showed 96% germination inhibition at 1000 ppm concentration of the pathogen *P. oryzae* and the complexes (Sl. No. 13, 15, 19 and 20) exhibit 70% germination inhibition of the pathogen *H. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration.

Study of the complexes of the type $(CoL_2) (NO_3)_2$ show that complexes (Sl. No. 23, 24 and 26) has 100% germination inhibition at 1000 ppm concentration of the pathogen *P. oryzae* and the complexes (Sl. No. 24, 25 and 26) exhibit 80% germination inhibition of the pathogen *H. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration.

By comparing the fungicidal activities of the complexes with that of the free ligands it is seen that the activity of the ligands increases considerably when they are co-ordinated with the metal ion cobalt. Further, the toxicity is noticed higher with the complexes of the type $(CoL_2) Cl_2$ and $(CoL_2) (NO_3)_2$. One interesting result is observed with the complex (Sl.

No. 13) in which the activity of the free ligand remained unchanged by co-ordinating it with the metal ion.

The fungicidal activities of the prepared complexes were compared with the standard fungicides like O-ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP, Derosal 60% WP which inhibited 95, 98, 87% spore germination of the pathogen at 1000 ppm concentration respectively. It was seen that 23 complexes (Sl. No. 1-4, 6-12, 14-20 and 22-26) inhibited spore germination in the range of the above standard fungicides, hence therefore can be used as commercial fungicides.

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